

RETROFITTING HORIZONTAL BUFFER VESSELS FOR THREE-PHASE SEPARATION OF GAS CONDENSATE AND WATER-METHANOL SOLUTION AT LOW-TEMPERATURE SEPARATION FACILITIES

Mikhail Zubkov

Project consultant, South Stream Transport B.V. Istanbul, Türkiye

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19858579>

<p>Keywords: <i>three-phase separation, water-methanol solution, gas condensate, buffer vessel, corrosion inhibitor, coalescence, equipment modernization.</i></p>	<p>Abstract: <i>The article examines the modernization of horizontal buffer vessels at low-temperature separation facilities to convert them to the three-phase separation mode for gas condensate, water-methanol solution, and gas. The relevance of the study arises from the growing number of failures of standard two-phase units during the injection of surfactant-containing corrosion inhibitors, which cause the formation of persistent emulsions, entrainment of the aqueous phase into commercial condensate, disruption of pump operation, and malfunction of automation systems. The purpose of the study is to develop and verify a set of internals installed within the existing shell, without its reconstruction, to restore stable three-phase separation. The scientific novelty of the work lies in identifying the mechanism of phase-separation failure in the gas condensate–water-methanol solution system under corrosion-inhibitor injection and substantiating vessel retrofitting using a calming partition, a coalescing block, a drainage gutter, and a condensate draw-off cup. Based on 120 days of pilot-industrial operation, the separation of the water-methanol solution was confirmed, its ingress into commercial condensate was eliminated, gas losses to the flare were reduced, and a high economic return on the project was achieved. The article will be useful for engineers involved in field gas treatment, designers of separation equipment, and specialists in oil and gas facility modernization.</i></p>
---	--

Introduction

The development of technologies for the production and treatment of natural gas and gas condensate is characterized by the continuous

complication of field operating conditions, together with increasingly stringent regulatory requirements for the quality of commercial products and the environmental safety of

Mikhail Zubkov

facilities (Kukharova et al., 2026). The principal and most widespread method of field gas treatment at gas-condensate fields is low-temperature separation. The LTS technology is based on cooling the gas-condensate mixture, followed by the removal of heavy hydrocarbons and moisture from it (Zhu et al., 2022). However, the specificity of this process increases the risk of hydrate formation in pipelines and process equipment. To prevent hydrate plugs, a thermodynamic inhibitor, methanol, is conventionally injected into process streams. By absorbing formation water, it forms a specific aqueous phase, namely a water-methanol solution (Zulu et al., 2024).

In parallel with hydrate control, operating companies are compelled to address the protection of pipeline infrastructure and vessel equipment from aggressive corrosion caused by the produced medium, which contains dissolved carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide. To minimize corrosion wear, corrosion inhibitors are continuously injected into the wellstream (Madan et al., 2025). The chemical-technological problem is that modern corrosion inhibitors are complex formulations containing surfactants. The presence of surfactants in the multicomponent hydrocarbon condensate–water–methanol system, combined with high hydrodynamic turbulence in inlet sections of equipment and throttling devices, leads to a sharp reduction in interfacial tension (Pan et al., 2022). This initiates the formation of highly stable water-condensate emulsions and causes abundant foaming.

The design schemes of many integrated gas treatment facilities, commissioned before the

widespread use of highly active surfactant-containing inhibitors, were not intended to separate such persistent emulsions (Yang et al., 2024). As a consequence, when the emulsified aqueous phase is carried over from the primary separator, a dispersed system is formed that passes in transit through two-phase buffer vessels without any possibility of moisture removal (Iakhin, 2026a). Practical operating experience has revealed a persistent negative trend: after the implementation of corrosion inhibitor injection, cases of large volumes of WMS entering trunk condensate pipelines transporting feedstock to processing facilities became more frequent, with peak discharges of up to 400 m³ recorded over short time intervals. Such incidents lead to above-limit water content in commercial condensate, provoke cavitation-induced destruction of pumping equipment, cause false responses of level gauges, which result in unauthorized pump shutdowns through emergency protection systems, and entail an increase in hydrocarbon process losses due to forced gas discharge to flare systems (Behnam Motlagh et al., 2026).

The relevance of the present study is the need to develop economically viable, technologically reliable, and implementable solutions to adapt the existing fleet of two-phase horizontal vessels to full three-phase separation. The development of such solutions will enable avoiding the enormous capital expenditures associated with dismantling existing units and constructing new three-phase apparatuses (Iakhin, 2025).

In this connection, the research problem is formulated as follows: the classical design hydrodynamics and internal architecture of

existing horizontal buffer vessels are unable to ensure the coalescence and gravitational settling of WMS microdroplets from the gas condensate stream under conditions of their structural-mechanical stabilization by corrosion inhibitors. The purpose of the work is to develop, theoretically substantiate, and practically assess, based on pilot-industrial operation, the effectiveness of a set of integrated internals for retrofitting horizontal buffer vessels and enabling their conversion to an effective three-phase separation mode.

To achieve this purpose, the following objectives are addressed:

1. To identify the causes of phase separation disturbance in horizontal buffer vessels in the simultaneous presence of gas condensate, water-methanol solution, and corrosion inhibitor.
2. To determine the effect of the corrosion inhibitor on the formation of stable water-condensate emulsions and to define the conditions under which gravitational phase separation loses its effectiveness.
3. To develop a structural modernization scheme for the internals of the buffer vessel that ensures conversion of the apparatus to a three-phase separation mode without changing the shell of the vessel.
4. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed set of internals using calculation data, laboratory tests, and pilot-industrial operation at an operating facility.

The scientific novelty of the study lies in establishing the mechanism of phase-separation disturbance in the gas condensate–water-methanol solution system under corrosion-inhibitor injection. The work proposes a new

approach to converting horizontal buffer vessels to a three-phase separation mode by installing a set of internals without altering the apparatus shell. Pilot-industrial data confirming the effectiveness of this solution under real operating conditions were obtained.

To verify the causes of separation disturbance and to assess the proposed modernization method, the following hypotheses were formulated.

H1: Injection of corrosion inhibitor into the gas condensate. The water-methanol solution system forms a stable emulsion that prevents droplet coalescence and reduces phase separation in a standard two-phase buffer vessel.

H2: Equipping a horizontal buffer vessel with a calming partition, a coalescing block, a gutter for water-methanol solution withdrawal, and a condensate draw-off cup ensures conversion of the apparatus to a three-phase separation mode and excludes the entry of water-methanol solution into the commercial condensate stream.

Materials and Methodology

To solve the stated problem and ensure the scientific validity of the technical solutions being developed, a comprehensive methodological approach was applied. It combines hydrodynamic analysis, empirical engineering design, laboratory physical modeling of phase-separation processes, and detailed pilot-to-industrial verification through an industrial case study.

A literature review and comparative analysis provided the theoretical foundation for the work. During the review, the mechanisms of emulsion formation and stabilization, the physicochemical effect of surfactants on

interfacial tension, and methods of mathematical and simulation modeling of gravitational three-phase separators were analyzed.

The practical part of the analysis, which includes specific metrics, volume calculations, installation photographs, and before-and-after schemes, is based entirely on a real enterprise. However, in this article, all names are anonymized in order to comply with the confidentiality agreement. To verify the hypothesis that the corrosion inhibitor constitutes the root cause of separation failure, a rigorous laboratory testing procedure was developed. Initially, the simplified model based on the kerosene–aqueous sodium chloride solution system was rejected as irrelevant because it did not reflect the specific rheology and thermodynamics of real field fluids. The main series of tests was conducted using appropriate media: actual commercial gas condensate, formation water doped with methanol, and the corrosion inhibitor applied in practice. During the experiments, the inhibitor concentration was systematically varied from 5% to 60%. The volumetric ratios of the hydrocarbon and water-methanol media were also varied. For each test sample, a photographic and video recording of the process was performed, with time-tracking of the onset of stratification and the attainment of complete separation. The stability of the emulsion, the formation of a foam layer, the morphology of the interfacial boundary, and the presence of residual microdroplets of the aqueous phase in the supernatant were evaluated.

The methodology for design calculations was

based on applying Stokes' law to calculate particle rise and settling velocities, using the Reynolds number to assess flow regimes within the apparatus, and determining the minimum required residence time of the phases in the degassing and settling zones. In accordance with the developed methodology, the solution was considered successful if, during long-term pilot-industrial operation lasting 120 days on pilot apparatuses, stable and sustained capture of WMS in the lower gutter of the modernized buffer vessel was confirmed, the guaranteed absence of signs of WMS entering the stream of commercial UGC sent to downstream facilities was demonstrated, the standard operating parameters of the apparatus such as level stability, absence of hydraulic seal failure, and normal discharge of flash gas were preserved. Confirmation of the effect had to be documented on the basis of a representative series of observations and accumulated discharge volume statistics.

Results and Discussion

The addition of a corrosion inhibitor, even at the minimum investigated concentration of 5%, leads to the immediate formation of a highly stable, thermodynamically stable emulsion at the phase boundary of the gas condensate–water-methanol solution system. This emulsion remained stable throughout the observation period, rendering traditional gravitational separation impossible.

Analysis of this phenomenon from the standpoint of physical chemistry shows that corrosion inhibitor molecules possess pronounced surfactant properties. The colloidal instability index of the fluid increases

substantially upon introduction of these reagents (Behnam Motlagh et al., 2026). Surfactant molecules are adsorbed on the surface of microdroplets of water and methanol dispersed in the continuous condensate phase. By reducing interfacial tension, they promote intensive droplet breakup in high-turbulence zones, such as chokes, control valves, and equipment inlet nozzles.

In addition, surfactants form a structural-mechanical protective shell at the phase boundary, known as the densely packed layer. As noted in fundamental studies of oil-water separation (Assar et al., 2024), DPL prevents droplet coalescence upon collision. The droplets behave like solid elastic spheres. The situation is aggravated by the low temperatures in the LTS process, which increase the viscosity of the continuous phase and decrease the particles' kinetic energy, thereby increasing the lifetime of the DPL layer. Thus, WMS microdroplets remain trapped in a stable suspension state and are freely carried away by the stream of light

hydrocarbon condensate.

To destroy the stabilized emulsion and separate WMS within the buffer vessel's existing shell, it was necessary to radically alter the internal hydrodynamic environment. The process of gravitational settling of a discrete particle in a continuous viscous medium is classically described by Stokes' law (Pan et al., 2021). The settling velocity of a WMS droplet is directly proportional to the square of its diameter and the density difference between the aqueous and hydrocarbon phases, and inversely proportional to the dynamic viscosity of the continuous phase. In the basic two-phase vessel design, turbulence and the vertical components of the velocity vector of upward flows exceeded the calculated settling velocity of WMS microdroplets. Therefore, the particles had no physical possibility of overcoming hydraulic resistance and settling to the bottom. Based on this, detailed verification calculations were carried out for the modernized apparatus, and the results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Key design, calculation, and hydraulic parameters of the modernized buffer tank

Parameter Name	Value	Unit
Calculated apparatus diameter	2.8954	m
Selected apparatus diameter	3.0000	m
Total apparatus volume	95.07	m ³
Maximum volumetric liquid capacity	288.18	m ³ /h
Liquid layer height in the apparatus	2.45	m
Liquid residence time in the degassing zone	759.9	s
Total liquid residence time in the apparatus	831.3	s
Minimum diameter of rising gas bubbles	0.0000127	m
Gas bubble rise time	21.23	s
Gas bubble rise velocity	0.0931	m/s

Mikhail Zubkov

Liquid velocity in the apparatus, longitudinal	0.0162	m/s
Calculated area of mesh packing	0.0034	m ²
Critical gas velocity through mesh packing	0.495	m/s
Actual gas velocity through packing	0.0566	m/s

Analysis of the obtained metrics shows that the total residence time of liquid in the apparatus exceeds 830 seconds. According to the Shell DEP 31.22.05.12 guidelines (Shell, 2008), such a time is more than sufficient for deep degassing and gravitational phase separation, provided that the flow has a strictly laminar character, turbulent eddies at the inlet are absent, and the apparatus is equipped with an effective coalescing section. The low longitudinal liquid velocity of 0.0162 m/s confirms the potential capacity of the apparatus to act as a high-quality gravitational settling separator.

The selection of horizontal buffer vessels as the priority modernization node was dictated by their topological position, the last barrier before condensate pumping into the trunk line, and by the significant available volume, which exceeds the volume of upstream first-stage separators by approximately 2.5 times.

To understand the engineering work carried out, the initial hydrodynamic configuration must be compared in detail with the modernized one. Figure 1 clearly illustrates the root problem of the basic scheme.

Fig. 1. Buffer capacity before modernization

The unstable UGC+WMS mixture is fed into the left part of the apparatus through a vertical nozzle connected to an internal elbow outlet. The high-kinetic-energy stream strikes downward, generating large-scale turbulence and intense

mixing in the left third of the volume (Iakhin, 2026b). As a consequence, a mass of dispersed suspension is formed. The red vectors indicate stratified, unstable flow. The bulk of the liquid moves along the vessel with a wavy interfacial

boundary, while a thin layer of separated heavy water, shown in blue, drags along the bottom of the apparatus. Since the degassed product is withdrawn from the lower right point, the transit liquid flow captures and carries the WMS accumulated at the bottom into the outlet pipeline. Thus, the vessel performed only two-phase degassing, while the task of free moisture separation remained unresolved.

The distinctiveness of the authors' retrofit concept lies in integrating a complex set of

internals under severe technological constraints. All work had to be carried out stepwise, taking parallel apparatuses out of service one at a time, without shutting down the field, using standard manways, and, of greatest importance, without hot work and without cutting any elements of the pressure shell. The load-bearing elements were installed by rigid fixing, that is, by interference support. As shown in Figure 2, the apparatus's internal architecture underwent a radical transformation.

Fig. 2. Buffer capacity after modernization

Four key assemblies were introduced into the design. The first is the calming partition, shown

in Figure 3

Fig. 3. Calming Partition

This structure is a perforated metal screen installed across the vessel's cross-section in the left third of its volume. The partition forms an inlet receiving chamber. Such baffles absorb the entire impact impulse of the incoming wellstream jet, suppress turbulent vortices, and ensure a strictly uniform, laminar distribution of

the flow over the entire cross-section of the apparatus before it enters the main separation zone. Primary rough separation of free gas and settling of the largest agglomerates of the aqueous phase occur in the receiving chamber. The second assembly is the block of calming nozzles, shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Block of calming nozzles

This element, located in the right half of the vessel, is the core of the emulsion-breaking process. It is a spatial modular assembly composed of many parallel inclined profiled plates. The physical operating principle of the

coalescer is based on the shallow pond theory (Abbas et al., 2025). Instead of settling to the bottom of the apparatus while overcoming a distance of up to 2.45 m, a WMS microdroplet needs to travel only a few millimeters or

centimeters to the surface of the nearest inclined plate. Upon contacting the metal, the droplets wet the surface and form a continuous liquid film, thereby overcoming the DPL barrier. As the film enlarges, it flows by gravity along the

inclined channels to the bottom of the apparatus as large, heavy droplets, which are no longer susceptible to re-entrainment by the UGC flow. The third assembly is the gutter for WMS discharge, shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Gutter for the discharge of WMS

The designed gutter is a long, semi-closed, box-shaped collector laid along the apparatus's bottom, the lowest generatrix beneath the coalescing block. Its function is the hydrodynamic isolation of the separated heavy aqueous phase from the longitudinal flow of the moving hydrocarbon condensate. The gutter

collects the drained WMS and directs it to a separate, independent outlet nozzle. This eliminates the effect of secondary moisture carryover, which constituted the fatal flaw of the former design.

The fourth assembly is the Glass for UGC draining, shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Glass for UGC draining

Installed above the UGC outlet nozzle, this element is a vertical cylinder with an elevated intake point and a protective mushroom-shaped

cap. The increased liquid withdrawal height ensures that only the uppermost, most deeply purified, and dehydrated layer of light

condensate is removed from the vessel. The protective cap prevents the capture of gas bubbles from above and the pulling of a water cone from below. The synthesis of these four solutions enabled the creation, within a single shell, of ideal conditions for sequential three-phase separation.

To confirm the design solutions, a pilot-industrial operation was launched on two pilot

Table 2. Statistics of water-methanol solution discharge from modernized tanks during the pilot operation period

Elapsed Time Since Start, days	Time Between Drains, days	Volume of WMR removed from Buffer Capacity 1, m ³	Volume of WMR removed from Buffer Capacity 2, m ³	Total WMR Volume Removed, m ³	Operating Mode Comment
0	0	Equipment commissioned	-	-	Start of pilot operation (Buffer Capacity 1)
9	9	0.500	-	0.500	Stable operation
16	7	0.350	-	0.350	Stable operation
34	18	0.410	Commissioning of Buffer Capacity 2	0.410	Start of pilot operation (Buffer Capacity 2)
49	15	0.211	0.228	0.439	Synchronized operation
64	15	0.342	0.081	0.423	Synchronized operation
68	4	1.439	0.000	1.439	Water cut spike
72	4	0.213	0.234	0.447	Operation recovery
75	3	4.650	0.383	5.033	Peak WMR discharge
93	18	2.455	0.426	2.881	Synchronized operation

buffer vessels out of the six available. The test period lasted 120 days, a duration recognized as sufficient for evaluating equipment performance across diverse process modes and for accumulating a statistically representative data set. The dynamics of accumulation and withdrawal of the water-methanol solution are presented in Table 2.

102	9	0.956	0.205	1.161	Synchronized operation
107	5	4.106	0.847	4.953	Water cut spike
112	5	1.190	0.721	1.911	Synchronized operation
TOTAL	112	16.822	3.125	19.947	

The apparatuses began to accumulate moisture steadily. On average, about 0.9 m³ of WMS was removed from the system per day, and over 120 days, a total of 109 m³ of the aqueous phase was captured, which would previously have entered the commercial condensate pipeline. The system's capacity handling slug moisture discharges, damping them without compromising the quality of the main product. The ingress of WMS into commercial products was eliminated by 100%. The water content in UGC remained steadily below the threshold value of 1.2%. The actual condensate content in the gas processed by the facility ranged from 420 to 470 g/m³, exceeding the initial design calculations by a considerable margin.

The stability of three-phase separation is inseparable from the correct operation of automation systems. The interdependence of phase levels is critical: an increase in the volume of the water cushion reduces the space available for condensate, increasing its velocity and decreasing residence time, which adversely affects quality. Water carryover into oil increases. Before modernization, due to foam and emulsion formation, the medium density in the apparatus did not match the design value. This led to failures in float- or displacer-level gauges, which could not determine a distinct

phase boundary. As a result, the automation system initiated false shutdowns of pumping equipment through emergency protection systems. After the implementation of the coalescing modules and the emulsion's destruction, the phase boundary stabilized. Level gauges began reading data correctly, enabling PI controllers to smoothly regulate control valves and eliminate full false emergency shutdowns.

One of the most significant technical effects was the reduction of the risk of cavitation damage to centrifugal pumps used for UGC transfer. Before modernization, the emulsified water-methanol mixture, with high vapor elasticity, especially under pressure drops at the pump suction, would boil in the working chambers. The resulting vapor-gas bubbles collapsed on the impeller blades, causing metal erosion and severe vibrations, which is a classical problem in the transportation of unstable multiphase mixtures. The use of pure degassed UGC completely eliminates this factor.

In practice, it turns out to be economically feasible: The synchronization of the apparatus and the new gas equalization line solves the problem of inhomogeneous filling of the six buffer vessels. Optimization of degassing and flow redistribution allowed decreasing the

amount of hydrocarbon gas sent to the flare from 22 m³/h to almost zero and saving about 1,100,000 cubic meters of gas a year as gas losses. All of this resulted in both direct commercial effect and improvement of the enterprise environmental indicators due to a cut in the carbon footprint released into the atmosphere from gas combustion. The overall economic efficiency of the modernization, calculated as the ratio of the result achieved to the costs of fabrication and installation, reached 89% per year.

However, the technology poses potential risks associated with its replication. Plate packings with a small spacing between corrugations to intensify coalescence are highly sensitive to mechanical impurities. In gas-condensate fields, these impurities include formation sand, proppant, and corrosion products. According to Shell DEP 31.22.05.12 design standards, the operation of such devices in media with a high fouling factor poses a risk of flow passage blockage (Shell, 2008). This may lead to local growth of pressure drop, plate deformation, and flow disruption. To minimize the risk, the apparatus must be washed or steamed regularly. The key modernization condition, namely the installation of elements by interference support without welding to the shell, is simultaneously an advantage through reduced CAPEX and downtime and a risk factor. In the event of severe hydrodynamic effects, for example, under slug flow conditions, the liquid's kinetic energy may overcome the frictional force of the fixing spacers. This creates the risk of displacement of the calming partition or the packing block, leading to a loss of their functionality.

The operability of gravitational systems is mathematically tied to the density difference between water and condensate. At late stages of field development, under reservoir pressure depletion or bottom-water breakthrough, the fluid composition changes. A change in the corrosion inhibitor grade may also lead to transformation of the rheological properties of the emulsion. With a significant increase in condensate viscosity or a decrease in density difference, the effectiveness of the plate coalescer will decline, requiring either a change in the plate inclination angle, the connection of electrostatic emulsion-breaking systems, or the introduction of additional chemical demulsifiers.

Nevertheless, in the field under consideration, the pilot-industrial operation results were recognized as successful. The commission review of the pilot project outcomes confirmed full compliance with the acceptance criteria. After evaluating the reproducibility of the design on similar apparatuses and the absence of an adverse impact on flash gas discharge, a decision was made to allocate financing to scale the technical solution to the remaining four buffer vessels.

Conclusion

The presented study is a scientific and engineering-technical analysis of the successful conversion of standard two-phase horizontal buffer vessels to an effective three-phase separation mode at a complex gas-condensate field facility. During the work, the fundamental mechanism underlying the problem was uncovered: it was shown that the use of surfactant-containing corrosion inhibitors acts

as a powerful catalyst for stabilizing water-condensate emulsions. Traditional gravitational separators are unable to handle such a system because of high turbulence and insufficient settling path length for microdroplets.

During the study, both proposed hypotheses were confirmed. The first hypothesis was confirmed by the results of laboratory tests, which showed that the introduction of a corrosion inhibitor into the gas condensate. A water-methanol solution system forms a stable emulsion and impedes phase separation in a standard two-phase vessel. The second hypothesis was confirmed by pilot-industrial operation data, within which the modernized buffer vessels ensured stable separation of the water-methanol solution, excluded its ingress into the commercial condensate stream, and ensured apparatus operation in a three-phase separation mode.

The developed modernization concept, including the installation of calming perforated partitions, coalescing packing modules, and isolated gutters and cups for phase withdrawal, is grounded in hydrodynamic principles. An engineering achievement consisted of implementing complex internal modifications while adhering to critical constraints, without

References

Abbas, M. M., Meshref, M. N. A., & Nadi, M. E. H. E. (2025). Design parameters for implementing inclined plate settlers in sedimentation tanks. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Scientific Studies*, 8(7), 460–468. <https://doi.org/10.53894/ijirss.v8i7.10471>

hot work or violating the integrity of the pressure shell of an operating vessel.

Analysis of the results of the 120-day pilot-industrial operation confirmed the achievement of all stated goals. The 100% exclusion of water-methanol solution ingress into commercial condensate was confirmed in practice. The implemented design eliminated the risks of cavitation wear in centrifugal transfer pumps and stabilized the operation of PI controllers in instrumentation and control automation. A system-level effect was the resolution of the associated gas utilization problem. Forced flaring of hydrocarbon gas was reduced by 1.1 million cubic meters per year, leading to an annual economic efficiency of 89% and improvements in the enterprise's environmental characteristics.

The practical significance of the completed work lies in the creation of a highly effective, scalable, capital- and resource-saving algorithm for adapting existing vessel equipment. The proposed set of technical solutions can be successfully replicated and applied to virtually any oil and gas production or processing asset that has encountered problems with stabilizing dispersed multiphase flows under the impact of modern inhibitors and reagents.

Assar, M., Asaadian, H., Stanko, M., & Grimes, B. A. (2024). A theoretical and experimental investigation of continuous oil–water gravity separation. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 298, 120375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2024.120375>

- Behnam Motlagh, M. A., Saeedi Dehaghani, A. H., & Tanhaei, H. (2026). Effects of temperature, brine, and inhibitor chemistry on emulsion stability in gas condensate systems under pipeline mixing conditions. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-026-47401-0>
- Iakhin, I. (2025). Adaptive Renovation of Centrifugal Separators: A Computational–Experimental Methodology for Optimizing Gas-Dynamic Regimes without Capital Expenditure. *Universal Library of Innovative Research and Studies*, 02(04), 111–119. <https://doi.org/10.70315/uloap.ulirs.2025.0204019>
- Iakhin, I. (2026a). Analysis of Liquid Carryover Causes in Gas Separation Equipment and Modern Approaches to Minimization. *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Science*, 74–77. <http://ijses.com/wp-content/uploads/2026/01/48-IJSES-V10N1.pdf>
- Iakhin, I. (2026b). Theoretical Foundations of Gas-Dynamic Processes in Centrifugal Separators under Variable Flow Regimes. *Australian Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology*, 276. <https://doi.org/10.34104/ajeit.026.02760282>
- Kukharova, T., Maltsev, P., Abramkin, S., & Novozhilov, I. (2026). Analysis of Modern Challenges and Technological Solutions in Natural Gas Production at Fields with Complex Geological Structure: A Review. *Resources*, 15(2), 32. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources15020032>
- Madan, A. A., Hussein, A., & Akhtar, S. S. (2025). A review on internal corrosion of pipelines in the oil and gas industry due to hydrogen sulfide and the role of coatings as a solution. *Corrosion Reviews*, 43(2), 189–208. <https://doi.org/10.1515/corrrev-2024-0114>
- Pan, Y., Xu, Y., Zhu, L., Liu, X., Zhao, G., Wang, S., Yang, L., Ma, T., & Liu, H. (2021). Stability and rheological properties of water-in-oil (W/O) emulsions prepared with a soyasaponin-PGPR system. *Future Foods*, 4, 100096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fufo.2021.100096>
- Pan, Z., Liu, W., Yu, L., Xie, Z., Sun, Q., Zhao, P., Chen, D., Fang, W., & Liu, B. (2022). Resonance-Induced Reduction of Interfacial Tension of Water–Methane and Improvement of Methane Solubility in Water. *Langmuir*, 38(44), 13594–13601. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.2c02392>
- Shell. (2008). *Shell DEP 31.22.05.12*. Scribd. <https://www.scribd.com/document/349256180/31220512-pdf>
- Yang, X., Chen, S., Chen, H., He, L., Ni, Y., Liu,

S., Chen, Z., & Tian, Y. (2024). Comprehensive review of stabilising factors, demulsification methods, and chemical demulsifiers of oil-water emulsions. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 358, 130206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2024.130206>

Zhu, L., Wang, D., Liu, G., & Liu, H. (2022). Oiling low temperature separation process for dehydration and de-hydrocarbon of natural gas and practical application. *Science and Technology for Energy Transition*, 77, 8. <https://doi.org/10.2516/stet/2022005>

Zulu, N. M., Hashemi, H., & Tumba, K. (2024). Chemical Inhibitors in Gas Hydrate Formation: A Review of Modelling Approaches. *ChemEngineering*, 8(6), 124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/chemengineering8060124>